

Global slavery of young people at home

Part 1

Artur Victoria

Introduction

I read this news paper article and got interested on it. So I got a study case.

It's a complex process that ruins economy of tax resources and causes serious psychological problems to young people.

“'Money mule' teenagers being recruited through social media by money laundering criminals”

By Leanne Clarke

Offenders will post an advert on social media looking to recruit people, offering “no risk” earnings in exchange for their account being used for funds to be transferred into and then a cash withdrawal by the account holder.

This cash is then handed over to someone identified by the suspect, usually in person. This can put the teenager at additional risk as they will not know the person they are meeting. The account holder receives a percentage of the funds, making this attractive to teenagers. Once one person has entered in to the agreement it is common for them to pass the details to their friends as a way of getting “easy money”. The teenager often does not appreciate that what they are doing is a crime, and sees this as victimless. They do not see where the money has come from or the crime type it goes on to fund.

What to look out for? Teenagers often having new clothes, accessories and technology or extra cash that cannot be explained. This is often passed around friendship groups, so look out for groups of friends discussing this or having extra money available. Teenagers talking about a new “friend” they may be in contact with suddenly who has helped them obtain cash or new clothes/items. **What to do if you suspect squaring is taking place?** Make sure the parents/guardians of the child are aware and report this to the bank and Police via 101. Money laundering carries the maximum sentence of 14 years imprisonment.

The begining

Based in Athens, and in Santa Monica - USA, LiveMe is a live streaming app that allows users to watch or stream live streaming videos available on iOS and Android devices. Invented by the Chinese and Russians, the consortium company was founded in 2016 by Yuki He. LiveMe was incubated by Cheetah Mobile, a Chinese mobile Internet company, and launched on the market in 2017.

Liveme is available in more than 85 countries and regions and supports nine languages. Liveme brought together twenty million users and, in eighteen months, the live streaming application processed more than \$ 6 million in payments to its influencers. Liveme currently has sixty million users, with 80% located in the United States.

Currently with more than 100 million active users, the company has a strong presence in the United States, China and the United Arab Emirates, and begins to invest in Brazil to grow in the Latin American region.

“We are growing in Brazil and Europe. Visibility is greater than Instagram (600,000 hours of daily content), ”said Cindy Wu, COO at LiveMe in Brazil. “USA is our most consolidated market, and we are growing in the United Arab Emirates. Brazil has more broadcasters than consumers. It is the 4th or 5th in the world ”.

Investors - IDG Capital Partners, Matrix Partners China, Gobi Partners, Cheetah Mobile, Evolution Media China, Welight Capital, ByteDance.

The company has a major implementation in the USA. In 2020, with COVID 19 it had 635 million monthly users worldwide, 2,000 employees - including more than 200 at its dual headquarters in California.

Majority shareholder Cheetah Mobile publicly trades on the New York Stock Exchange, giving partners additional credibility and flexibility to make acquisitions. Although the stock price has been halved in the last year to about \$ 9.70, the company remains a \$ 1 billion company.

Business - On LiveMe, digital influencers broadcast live videos, interact with Internet users via chat and receive virtual gifts from viewers. Gifts arrive through virtual coins and diamonds. The app has a gamification that allows broadcasters to earn more coins

and diamonds if they meet challenges on the platform, such as making a Live with a few thousand users.

On the platform, 350 diamonds equals US \$ 1. While 15 coins are worth R \$ 0.99. The earnings share is 30% for influencers (here called transmitters) and 70% for social media. Purchases are made by credit card. However, the executive believes that there is potential to have other means of payment on the platform.

The app and broadcasters generate revenue when viewers buy virtual gifts. Top users are earning a sum of five digits a week

Influencers

Bringing a little of this scenario to Brazil, LiveMe presented to the press three examples of broadcasters that are successful on the platform. These young women live and interact with users daily. Influencers receive gifts such as an iPhone, a R \$ 1,000 voucher for travel at CVC, an international trip, going to Rock in Rio with everything paid for in September, as well as revenues that can vary from R \$ 4,000 to R \$ 6,000.

Wu and two other executives run the operation in an office inside WeWork Paulista, in São Paulo.

When asked about privacy, Cindy Wu of LiveMe said that there are 160 auditors and an artificial intelligence application to ensure the platform works smoothly, once the profiles are open - anyone can see someone else's broadcast.

Partnerships - Live.me has partnerships with Instagram, Twitter and Facebook, so that its users can reference their profiles on these social networks on the platform, interconnecting them.

How the business works and its ethics.

Installation

When installing the application on IOS or Android operating system (live.me lite as it has fewer options)

- You have to choose a fictitious name or simply leave it blank and the system assigns an identification number with ten digits in each case.
- You have to upload one or more photos (for identification purposes and to attract future supporters as we will explain.
- Put what you like to do or a personal presentation.

- Indicates whether you want to be integrated into the members network as a gift giver (gifter) or as a transmitter (broadcaster).

If you choose the first option you should buy diamonds to offer to those who will transmit, there are two options here:

a) Purchase on the website with a credit card;

b) Purchase from resellers (individuals who belong to the network and are dedicated to buying large quantities of diamonds (us dollars) selling them a little cheaper than on the website. The payment method varies depending on the reseller, be it paypal, card credit cards or even bitcoins or other undetectable virtual payments.

Resellers

Becoming a reseller is a lucrative job. Live.me recommends resellers authorised so a Gifter or user instead of buying coins in the site buy to the reseller using the most diferents ways of payment, getting the advantage of being anonymous or buying cheaper those virtual coins.

Live.me and resellers are a part of the business.

US Reseller Offer Thru PayPal —Starting Oct 28th,2019					
Recharge Amount	Coins on Website	Bonus	Number of Coins	Coins/\$1	Addl Benefits
\$52	4440	1.1	5000	97	
\$100	8900	1.1	9800	98	
\$200	17800	1.1	19600	98	
\$300	26700	1.1	29400	98	
\$400	35800	1.1	39400	98.5	
\$500	44500	1.124	50000	100	1 EXP card
\$1,000	90000	1.14	102,000	102	1 EXP card+100fan card
\$1,500	13500	1.14	153,000	102	
\$2,000	180,000	1.15	207,000	103.5	2 EXP card+200fan card
\$2,500	225,000	1.15	258,750	103.5	
\$3,000	270,000	1.15	310,500	103.5	3 EXP card+300fan card
\$5,000	450,000	1.18	531,000	106.2	5 EXP card+500fan card
\$10,000	900,000	1.18	1,062,000	106.2	10 EXP card+1k fan card

NOTE – AS SEEN TRANSACTIONS GO TO 10 THOUSAND USD

What is an Agency

If you choose to be a Broadcaster recognized by Live.me you must do an interview at a Live.me agency

The Agency is a person who recruits slaves to perform at Live.me although they receive a salary based on the gifts they receive from other members of the network.

The application for application to be a recruiting agent is made by filling out a google form with the following text:

Agency Leader Recruitment

Yayyy !! Liveme need you as the agency leaders !! You can help us expand and train new broadcasters with your talents and hard work !! Requirements: provide 15 contracted broadcasters each month. If you are interested, please fill in the following information. If you pass the screening, official staff will contact you. Thank you for your support.

- What kind of broadcasters do you think will be popular on liveme? *
- How do you recruit new broadcasters from offsite? *
- What states can you recruit from USA / Canada / Australia / NewZealand / United Kingdom? *
- How many new broadcasters can you bring to LiveMe every month? *
- What ways do you use to train broadcasters that can make them become professional broadcasters soon? *
- Your LiveMe id *
- How many fans do you have on Liveme? *
- How many diamonds have you earned lately, approximately? *
- Your name *
- The country, state and city you live in *

Your age *

- Your WhatsApp number *
- Your Email *
- Are you a contracted broadcaster? *
- Your work experience (in details) *

What does an Agency do and what are the gains

An agency is the interlocutor between Broadcaster and Operative Managers who analyze the professionals involved and their performance in terms of diamond gains (1 diamond = 1 usd). You also have to collaborate on campaigns and events that Live.me does weekly or monthly (for example the zodiac party).

The agency earns a percentage of what its broadcasters earn. (180 people per year) accumulated with the others from previous years. Let's say for example if a broadcaster has to earn a minimum of ten thousand diamonds per month - be it 120 thousand diamonds per year (equivalent to 120 thousand USD) 180 broadcasters annually contribute to the agency with a total of two million one hundred and sixty thousand USD.

Broadcaster what it does and what are the gains

The Broadcaster has obligations:

- 1 - Make 15 transmissions per month, each of them at least two hours each, or 30 hours per month
- 2 - Earn from Gifters a minimum of 10,000 diamonds per month.

The levels

To entice users both gifters and broadcasters, levels are created that provide perks and bonuses. To access the higher level it is necessary or make many transmissions. Receive lots of diamonds (for broadcasters) and (for gifters) give lots of gifts and buy lots of diamonds.

From each level to the next, the number of demands and degree of effort is exaggeratedly multiplied.

The gains

Broadcaster Data			Gift/Diamond Exchange (Rate: 350 diamonds =1\$)	Bonus for broadcaster (\$)	Diamonds
Level	Diamonds (per month)	Broadcast length (days and hours per month)			
10	5000000	15/30	14286	4500	1575000
9	3000000	15/30	8571	3000	1050000
8	2000000	15/30	5714	2500	875000
7	1000000	15/30	2857	1500	525000
6	500000	15/30	1429	1000	350000
5	200000	15/30	571	400	140000
4	100000	15/30	286	250	87500
3	50000	15/30	143	150	52500
2	30000	15/30	86	90	31500
1	10000	15/30	29	30	10500

NOTE – 1 diamond = 1usd

One broadcaster of level 10 can earn a salary of 5 millions diamonds a month. However when changing the rate becomes 350 diamonds for 1 usd, getting a bonus of 4.500 usd.

The Gifter

A professional gifter also earn money. Logical he does not buy ten thousand usd of coins just for fun. He can earn accordingly this table

• Gifter Reward •

The Top 20 gifters in each group will receive the following rewards.

Ranking	Lv.0-40	Lv.41-70	Lv.71-100
Top 1	\$800	\$1500	\$3000
Top 2	\$500	\$800	\$2000
Top 3	\$300	\$500	\$1000
Top 4-5	\$200	\$300	\$800
Top 6-10	\$100	\$200	\$500
Top 11-20	\$80	\$100	\$200

All cash rewards will be delivered as diamond reward based on the

NOTE – A gifter can earn 3 THOUSAND usd if he is in level 70

Rolling on the site you can see gifters or Broadcasters with 100 millions of diamonds that means Euro: 28.571,42857142857

The double loop

Of course a gifter and a Broadcaster can do a Loop to wash money so they agree and even out of broadcast time they can give gifts and those spent virtual coins are converted in diamonds and the diamonds in Usd and they the Broadcaster can convert the gifts in diamonds getting paid or just change with coins to give them back to the gifter.

The Broadcaster or professional gifter has to have an account on Payoneer. Payoneer is a financial services company that provides online money transfer, digital payment services and provides customers with working capital.

Account holders can send and receive funds into their bank account, Payoneer e-wallet, or onto a re-loadable prepaid MasterCard debit card that can be used online or at points of sale

The company specializes in facilitating cross-border B2B payments. It provides cross-border transactions in 200 countries and territories and more than 150 local currencies, with its cross border wire transfers, online payments, and refillable debit card services.

he company is headquartered in New York City. As of 2019, the company employed approximately 1,200 people, and serves over 4 million customers in 14 offices around the world. In 2019 the company was valued at over \$1 billion.

In order to lawfully remit money within the European Single Market, Payoneer is registered with the Gibraltar Financial Services Commission.

How the Broadcaster or Gifter controls the money transactions and diamonds transferred

References:

1. ↑ Russell, Jon (2 de maio de 2017). «Cheetah Mobile's Live.me streaming service raises \$60M from Chinese investors». TechCrunch
2. ↑ Soo, Zen (20 de Julho de 2018). «Meet the Chinese live-streaming app Live.me that's taking the US by storm». South China Morning Post